

Bayesian Sparse Financial Networks*

Mauro Bernardi^{†1} and Michele Costola^{‡2}

¹Department of Statistical Sciences, University of Padova and Istituto per le Applicazioni del Calcolo “Mauro Picone” - CNR, Roma, Italy

²Research Center SAFE, House of Finance, Goethe University Frankfurt, Germany

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Abstract

We propose a Bayesian approach to the problem of variable selection and shrinkage in high dimensional sparse regression models where the regularisation method is an extension of a previous LASSO. The model allows us to include a large number of institutions which improves the identification of the relationship and maintains at the same time the flexibility of the univariate framework. Furthermore, we obtain a weighted directed network since the adjacency matrix is built “row by row” using for each institutions the posterior inclusion probabilities of the other institutions in the system.

KEYWORDS: Financial Networks, Bayesian inference, Lasso, Elastic Net, Sparsity, Spike and Slab prior.

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[†]Corresponding author. Via C. Battisti, 241, 35121 Padua, Italy. e-mail: mauro.bernardi@unipd.it, Phone.: +39.049.8274165.

[‡]Theodor-W.-Adorno-Platz 3, 60323 Frankfurt am Main, Germany. e-mail: costola@safe.uni-frankfurt.de, www.safe-frankfurt.de, Phone: +49 69 798 34505, Fax +49 69 798 30077.

1 Introduction

During the last decade, the analysis of the financial system and its interconnectedness has become increasingly important because they provide relevant insights both on the financial stability of the whole economic system and for the management of risk and capital allocation. Literature presented theoretical models on financial network (Allen and Babus, 2009; Elliott et al., 2014; Acemoglu et al., 2015) and empirical papers on network inference and estimation (Diebold and Yilmaz, 2014; Bianchi et al., 2015; Ahelegbey et al., 2016; Barigozzi and Brownlees, 2016; Billio et al., 2018, 2016; Demirer et al., 2017; Korobilis and Yilmaz, 2018). Regarding the last stream of literature, Billio et al. (2012) propose a bivariate Granger causality to test for network linkages on firms' financial returns. Even if this approach is very flexible since is tested pairwise and thus can be applied to any dataset of any dimension, the transmission mechanism (the linkages) cannot be correctly identified because shocks are not jointly considered at the same time. As recently noted by Acharya et al. (2012), it cannot be distinguished if one firm Granger causes another or a third one causes both. Given the above considerations, the best candidates to describe the structural shocks in the system are multivariate models such as Vector Autoregressive (VAR) models. Among other, Diebold and Yilmaz (2014) propose connectedness measures derived from the variance decomposition built on the VAR model. Clearly, VAR models suffer the well known curse of dimensionality and thus limit their field of analysis to low dimensional settings. To overcome this issue, new methodologies start to be proposed in order to deal with high-dimensional data using the LASSO approach of Tibshirani (1996). This seminal paper introduced the least absolute shrinkage and selection operator (LASSO), one of the most popular method that can simultaneously perform parameters estimation and selection in regression models. Among the most important shrinkage methods proposed in the literature there are the least angle regression (LARS) of Efron et al. (2004), the adaptive LASSO of Zou (2006) and the group LASSO of Yuan and Lin (2006). In the network perspective, Barigozzi and Brownlees (2016) propose the NETS algorithm based on LASSO approach and model a large VAR (90 U.S. bluechips across different industries) where the autoregressive matrices and the inverse covariance matrix of the innovations are sparse. In the spirit of Diebold and Yilmaz (2014), Demirer et al. (2017) apply the LASSO methodology to estimate a global bank network which includes the world's top 150 banks during the period from 2003 to 2014. Our paper contributes to this stream of literature. We propose a flexible approach to the problem of variable selection and shrinkage in high dimensional sparse models where the regularisation method is an extension of a previous LASSO in a Bayesian framework. The proposed model can be interpreted as a VAR model with a diagonal covariance matrix where shocks are instantaneously uncorrelated where the number of covariates is strictly larger than the number of observations. We aim to

improve the identification of the relationship (linkages) among the financial firms by including a very large number of institutions at different lags in each equation by maintaining *de facto* the flexibility of the univariate framework. The model accounts for two sets of covariates. The first set contains the predetermined variables which cannot be penalized. These variables are the autoregressive component of the given financial institution (dependent variable) and can be lagged state variables such as financial and macroeconomic factors which describe the state of economy as in [Adrian and Brunnermeier \(2016\)](#). The second set contains all the (lagged) financial institutions in the system that can be included at a given probability. The estimation of the network is part of the process and is straightforward. For a given institution, the ingoing financial linkages are directly derived by the (posterior) inclusion probability. Consequently, we have a weighted directed network where the adjacency matrix is built “row by row”, that is equation by equation, using for each institutions the posterior inclusion probabilities of the other institutions in the financial system.

In the empirical analysis, we consider the weekly closing price series of 1248 world financial firms (banks, insurances and financial services) active and dead from the 29th December 2000 to 6th October 2017 and estimate the networks over time using a rolling window approach. Then, we analyse the out-degree distribution during the considered period which usually exhibits the heavy-tailed property of scale-free networks. This is due to the heterogeneity of the financial linkages ([Barabási and Albert, 1999](#); [Barabási and Bonabeau, 2003](#); [Boss et al., 2004](#)). To test it, we use the Generalized Pareto distribution and estimate the tail index of the out-degree distribution over time. Given the its behaviour in term of persistence, we select the MSCI World Financials index as the proxy of the considered market and show, after controlling for volatility and volatility-in mean effect, that the tail index is a significant predictor of the market at the first lag (one week) and at the fourth lag (one month).

The remaining of the paper is structured as follows. Section 2 introduces and formalises the main problem we deal in this paper, namely the identification and estimation of large dimensional Networks using dynamic regression models. Section 3 introduces the sparse heteroskedastic linear regression approach used to estimate the Network and the Stochastic Search Variable Selection Expectation–Maximisation SSVS–EM algorithm that uses a Spike–and–Slab prior to select the relevant coefficients. Section 4 illustrates the empirical analysis and our major findings and Section 5 concludes.

2 General framework for Network analysis

In this Section, we introduce the general framework we propose for the network analysis using the Vector Autoregressive (VAR) approach. To this end, we develop a framework for the equation–

by-equation estimation of the VAR parameters by Bayesian dynamic sparse heteroskedastic linear regression methods where an additional latent indicator having a Spike-and-Slab prior distribution is included to probabilistically assess the relevance of each institutions in the network. We also address the relevant issue that the proposed equation-by-equation estimating approach fails to adequately account for the cross-section correlation among the regression residuals which is likely to bias the resulting parameter estimates. We address this issue by modelling the cross-section correlation in the residuals as the result of an $f \times 1$ vector of common factors. In this way, we are able to separate the systematic and idiosyncratic components of the error process, thereby aligning our approach with the large literature on the distinction between systematic and idiosyncratic risks (see for a recent example which focuses on credit spreads).

2.1 VAR model

Consider the random vector $\mathbf{y}_t = (y_{1,t}, y_{2,t}, \dots, y_{N,t})'$ collecting the returns $y_{i,t} \in \mathbb{R}$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, N$ of the financial institutions at time $t = 1, 2, \dots, T$. We consider the following VAR model which expresses the cross-section returns of all the institutions at time t as a function of the lagged returns:

$$\mathbf{y}_t = \boldsymbol{\mu} + \sum_{j=1}^k \boldsymbol{\Phi}_j \mathbf{y}_{t-j} + \boldsymbol{\eta}_t, \quad (1)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\mu} \in \mathbb{R}^N$ is a vector of constant terms, $\boldsymbol{\Phi}_j$ is the $(N \times N)$ autoregressive matrix of loading parameters at the j -th lag and $\boldsymbol{\eta}_t \sim \mathbf{N}(0, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_\eta)$. As extensively explained in the Introduction and below in Section 4 the cross-sectional dimension of the vector N in our application is very large, i.e., $N \gg 100$ preventing the estimation of the joint VAR model in equation (1) using likelihood-based procedures. Nonetheless, given that each equation in (1) shares a common set of right hand side variables, the estimation problem has a seemingly unrelated regressions (SUR) structure which has led researchers to pursue an equation-by-equation strategy using ordinary least squares. Nevertheless, it is clear that this approach sets the off-diagonal elements of the covariance matrix of the error term $\boldsymbol{\eta}_t$ to zero, which amounts to the assumption of cross-section independence, thereby leading to biased parameter estimates. We address this issue by modelling the cross-section correlation in the residuals as the result of an $f \times 1$ vector of common factors. In this way, we are able to separate the systematic and idiosyncratic components of the error process, thereby aligning our approach with the large literature on the distinction between systematic and idiosyncratic risks (see , for a recent example which focuses on credit spreads). Furthermore, where one wishes to analyse spillover effects between variables, it is important to focus on the idiosyncratic variation having purged any systematic variation or else one is likely to obtain a biased estimate of the spillover intensity, a phenomenon that we demonstrate in

Section 4.1 below. Formally, we assume that:

$$\boldsymbol{\eta}_t = \mathbf{F}\mathbf{f}_t + \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_t, \quad (2)$$

where \mathbf{f}_t is a vector of common factors, \mathbf{F} is a matrix of dimension $(N \times f)$ of heterogeneous factor loadings and $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_t \sim \mathbf{N}(0, \boldsymbol{\Omega})$ contains the idiosyncratic components of $\boldsymbol{\eta}_t$ which are mutually uncorrelated but not homoskedastic such that $\boldsymbol{\Omega} = \text{diag}\{\boldsymbol{\Omega}_{1,1}, \boldsymbol{\Omega}_{2,2}, \dots, \boldsymbol{\Omega}_{N,N}\}$ is diagonal. Combining equations (1) and (2) yields the following factor VAR model:

$$\mathbf{y}_t = \boldsymbol{\mu} + \sum_{j=1}^k \boldsymbol{\Phi}_j \mathbf{y}_{t-j} + \mathbf{F}\mathbf{f}_t + \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_t, \quad (3)$$

for $t = 1, 2, \dots, T$.

The factors, \mathbf{f}_t , may be either observed or latent but we limit our attention to the case of observed factors. This confers at least two benefits relative to unobserved factor approaches such as principal components analysis (e.g., Bai, 2003, 2009) or the common correlated effects framework of Pesaran (2006). First, it is often easier to achieve an economically meaningful interpretation of observed factors than latent factors. Second, an observed factor structure is parsimonious and can be feasibly implemented in relatively small datasets. By contrast, the reliable estimation of principal components requires a relatively high-dimensional dataset. Likewise, the common correlated effects approach can lead to a proliferation of estimated parameters because the unobserved common factors are approximated by augmenting the model with p lags of the cross-section averages of \mathbf{y}_t .

Given that the error terms in (4) are uncorrelated by construction, the model can be estimated equation-by-equation linear regression without loss of generality. To illustrate the regression procedure, it is useful to first re-write the i -th equation of equation (4) compactly as follows:

$$y_{i,t} = \mu + \mathbf{x}'_{i,t} \boldsymbol{\beta}_i + \mathbf{z}'_t \boldsymbol{\varphi}_i + \varepsilon_{i,t}, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, N, \quad (4)$$

for $t = 1, 2, \dots, T$, where $\mu \in \mathbb{R}$ is the intercept, \mathbf{x}_t is a $(kN \times 1)$ vector containing all of the endogenous lagged (predetermined) regressors $(y_{1,t-1}, y_{2,t-1}, \dots, y_{N,t-1}, y_{1,t-2}, y_{2,t-2}, \dots, y_{N,t-2}, \dots, y_{1,t-k}, y_{2,t-k}, \dots)$. $\boldsymbol{\beta}_i$ contains the corresponding regression coefficients, \mathbf{z}_t is the $(f \times 1)$ vector of factors common to all the institutions accounting for the unexplained cross-sectional dependence, $\boldsymbol{\varphi}_i$ contains the corresponding coefficients and $\varepsilon_{i,t} \sim \mathbf{N}(0, \sigma_i^2)$ which are assumed independent $\varepsilon_{i,t} \perp \varepsilon_j$, for $i \neq j$ but not homoskedastic. Specifically we impose the usual assumption that the conditional distribution of the error term follows ARCH-type process of Engle and Bollerslev (1986) to capture the autocorrelations of squared returns.

In Section 3 we cast the regression model (4) in a Bayesian framework, then we introduce an algorithm for efficiently dealing with Maximum–a–Posteriori estimation of the relevant regression parameters as well as the parameters driving the variance of the error term. We assume a Spike–and–Slab prior on the endogenous regressors parameters β featuring the presence of irrelevant regressors, i.e., $\beta_j = 0$ for some j in a probabilistic way, while retaining the common factor structure \mathbf{z}_t . For the sake of simplicity in Section 3 we will suppress the dependence on the institution indicator i .

2.2 Network estimation

For sake of clarity, we rewrite the model of Equation 4 to highlight its components in term of network linkages. We consider the model up to 1 lag:

$$y_{i,t} = \mu_i + \alpha y_{i,t-1} + \sum_{j=1}^{n_t-1} \underbrace{\beta_j X_{j,t-1}}_{\text{with prob. } \hat{\pi}_{i,j}} + \varepsilon_{i,t}, \quad (5)$$

for $i = 1, \dots, n_t$, $\varepsilon_{i,t}$ follows a GARCH(1,1) process and $i \neq j$. The term $\alpha y_{i,t-1}$ refers to the autoregressive component which is included by default in the model and $\hat{\pi}_{i,j}$ is the estimated inclusion probability of the institution j for the institution i as detailed in the next Section. We further assume that $\varepsilon_i \perp \varepsilon_j$, for $i \neq j$.

In general, we can define a network as a set of nodes $V_t = \{1, 2, \dots, n_t\}$ and directed edges between nodes which can be represented through an n_t -dimensional adjacency matrix A_t

$$A_t = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & a_{1,2,t} & \cdots & a_{1,j-1,t} & a_{1,j,t} & \cdots & a_{1,n_t,t} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \cdots & \ddots & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \cdots & \cdots & \ddots & \cdots & \cdots & \vdots \\ a_{i,1,t} & \cdots & \cdots & a_{i,j-1,t} & a_{i,j,t} & \cdots & a_{i,n_t,t} \\ \vdots & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ a_{n_t,1,t} & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (6)$$

where $a_{i,j,t} = g(\hat{\pi}_{i,j,t})$ is a function of the estimated inclusion probabilities $\hat{\pi}_{i,j,t}$. Given the described model, different characterisation of the network are possible (i.e complete or incomplete network). Indeed, the matrix A_t is asymmetric and describes a weighted network since the linkages are defined in terms of the inclusion probabilities and thus, the element $a_{i,j,t}$ indicates a (weighted) edge from i directed to j with $i, j \in V_t$. For instance, using a given threshold c , we might have the inclusion/exclusion of y_j by selecting $g(\hat{\pi}_{i,j,t}) = \mathbb{1}_{(c,\infty)}(\hat{\pi}_{i,j,t})$ in the adjacency

matrix A_t . In this case, we have binary relationship, i.e., the element $a_{i,j,t}$ is equal to 1 if $\widehat{\pi}_{i,j} > c$ and thus there is edge from i directed to j with $i, j \in V_t$ and 0, otherwise. Another possibility is the use of multiple thresholds to have different category of linkages in the network (i.e., low–medium–high). In this application, since we are interested to proxy the (strong) financial linkages, we consider the binary case with one threshold and thus, we select the regressors with a probability of inclusion higher than $c = 95\%$.

3 Heteroskedastic Spike–and–Slab SSVS–EM

3.1 The Model

Let $\mathbf{y} = (y_1, y_2, \dots, y_T)'$ be the vector of observations on the scalar response variable Y , $\mathbf{x}_t = (x_{1,t}, x_{2,t}, \dots, x_{p,t})'$ be the $(p \times 1)$ vector of observations on the p endogenous covariates, and let $\mathbf{z}_t = (z_{1,t}, z_{2,t}, \dots, z_{f,t})'$ the $(f \times 1)$ vector of common factors that are never excluded from the regression. We consider the following heteroskedastic regression model

$$\pi(y_t | \mathbf{x}_t, \mathbf{z}_t, \mu, \boldsymbol{\beta}, \boldsymbol{\varphi}, \sigma_\varepsilon^2) = \phi\left(y_t | \mu + \mathbf{x}'_t \boldsymbol{\beta} + \mathbf{z}'_t \boldsymbol{\varphi}, h_t^{\frac{1}{2}}\right), \quad (7)$$

$$h_t = \gamma_h + \alpha_h \varepsilon_{t-1}^2 + \beta_h h_{t-1}, \quad (8)$$

where $\mu \in \mathbb{R}$ denotes the parameter related to the intercept of the model, $\boldsymbol{\beta} = (\beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_p)' \in \mathbb{R}^p$ is a vector of dimension $(p \times 1)$ regression parameters, $\boldsymbol{\varphi} \in \mathbb{R}^f$ is a vector of dimension $(f \times 1)$ of factors' loading parameters and $h_t \in \mathbb{R}^+$ is the variance of the innovation term ε_t which is assumed to follow a weekly stationary GARCH(1,1) process with parameters $\gamma_h > 0$, $\alpha_h \geq 0$ and $\beta_h \geq 0$ and $\alpha_h + \beta_h < 1$. Hereafter, $\varepsilon_{t-j} = y_{t-j} - \mu - \mathbf{x}'_{t-j} \boldsymbol{\beta} - \mathbf{z}'_{t-j} \boldsymbol{\varphi}$, for any $j \geq 0$ and for convenience we set $h_0 = y_0 = 0$. Moreover, we collect the GARCH parameters in the vector $\boldsymbol{\psi} = (\gamma_h, \alpha_h, \beta_h)$.

3.2 Prior specification

Using standard notation, let $\boldsymbol{\gamma}$ be the p -vector where $\gamma_j = 1$ if the j -th covariate x_j is included as explanatory variable in the regression model and $\gamma_j = 0$, otherwise. Assuming that $\gamma_j \sim \mathcal{Ber}(\omega)$,

the prior distribution for β_j , $j = 1, 2, \dots, p$ can be written as the mixture

$$\mu \sim \text{N}(\mu \mid \mu_\mu, \sigma_\mu^2) \quad (9)$$

$$(\boldsymbol{\beta} \mid \boldsymbol{\gamma}) \sim \text{N}(\boldsymbol{\beta} \mid 0, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_\beta) \quad (10)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\varphi} \sim \text{N}(\boldsymbol{\varphi} \mid \boldsymbol{\mu}_\varphi, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_\varphi) \quad (11)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_\beta = \text{diag}\{b_1, b_2, \dots, b_p\} \quad (12)$$

$$b_j = (1 - \gamma_j) \nu_0 + \gamma_j \nu_{1,j}, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, p \quad (13)$$

$$\nu_1 \sim \prod_{j=1}^p \frac{\nu_{1,j}^b (1 - \nu_{1,j})^{-a-b-2}}{\text{Be}(a+1, b+1)} \mathbb{1}_{(0,\infty)}(\nu_{1,j}) \quad (14)$$

$$\omega \sim \frac{\omega^{a-1} (1 - \omega)^{b-1}}{\text{Be}(a, b)} \quad (15)$$

$$\gamma_h \sim \text{N}(\gamma_h \mid \mu_\gamma, \sigma_\gamma^2) \mathbb{1}_{(0,\infty)}(\gamma_h) \quad (16)$$

$$\alpha_h, \beta_h \sim \text{N}(\alpha_h \mid \mu_\alpha, \sigma_\alpha^2) \times \text{N}(\beta_h \mid \mu_\beta, \sigma_\beta^2) \times \mathbb{1}_{\mathcal{S}}(\alpha_h, \beta_h), \quad (17)$$

where $b = 0$, $a \in (-1, 0]$ and \mathcal{S} denotes the simplex $\alpha_h > 0$, $\beta_h > 0$ and $\alpha_h + \beta_h < 1$ and $\mathbb{1}_A(x)$ is the indicator function that takes value 1 if and only if $x \in A$. Common choices for the parameter a is $a = -\frac{3}{4}$. Hereafter, $\boldsymbol{\vartheta} = (\mu, \boldsymbol{\beta}', \boldsymbol{\varphi}', \omega, \boldsymbol{\nu}_1, \boldsymbol{\psi}')'$ collects all the unknown parameters that should be estimated.

3.3 SSVS–EM algorithm

Hereafter, we focus on the EM algorithm which has been previously applied to the case of finite mixtures of univariate Student–t distributions by [Peel and McLachlan \(2000\)](#). For the purpose of application of the EM algorithm the vector of observations $\{y_t, \mathbf{x}_t, \mathbf{z}_t\}$, for $t = 1, 2, \dots, T$ is regarded as being incomplete. Following the implementation described in [Peel and McLachlan \(2000\)](#) in a finite mixture context, a missing data structure γ_t , $\forall t = 1, 2, \dots, T$ that relies to the Spike–and–Slab mixture representation in equation (10) is introduced leading to the following

complete-data log-likelihood:

$$\begin{aligned} \log \mathcal{L}_c(\boldsymbol{\vartheta}) &= -\frac{T}{2} \log(2\pi) - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{t=1}^T \log(h_t) - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{t=1}^T \frac{\|y_t - \mu - \mathbf{x}'_t \boldsymbol{\beta} - \mathbf{z}'_t \boldsymbol{\varphi}\|_2^2}{h_t} \\ &\quad - \frac{p}{2} \log(2\pi) - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=1}^p \log(b_j) - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=1}^p \frac{\beta_j^2}{b_j} \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\quad + |\gamma| \log\left(\frac{\omega}{1-\omega}\right) + p \log(1-\omega) \\ &\quad - (a+b+2) \sum_{j=1}^p \log(1+\nu_{1,j}) + b \sum_{j=1}^p \log(\nu_{1,j}) - \sum_{j=1}^p \log(\text{Be}(a+1, b+1)) \\ &\quad + (a-1) \log(\omega) + (b-1) \log(1-\omega) - \log(\text{Be}(a, b)) \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{2} \log(2\pi) - \frac{1}{2} \log(\sigma_\gamma^2) - \frac{1}{2} \frac{(\gamma h - \mu_\gamma)^2}{\sigma_\gamma^2} \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

$$- \frac{1}{2} \log(2\pi) - \frac{1}{2} \log(\sigma_\alpha^2) - \frac{1}{2} \frac{(\alpha_h - \mu_\alpha)^2}{\sigma_\alpha^2} \quad (20)$$

$$- \frac{1}{2} \log(2\pi) - \frac{1}{2} \log(\sigma_\beta^2) - \frac{1}{2} \frac{(\beta_h - \mu_\beta)^2}{\sigma_\beta^2} \quad (21)$$

$$- \frac{f}{2} \log(2\pi) - \frac{1}{2} \log|\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_\varphi| - \frac{1}{2} (\boldsymbol{\varphi} - \boldsymbol{\mu}_\varphi)' \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_\varphi^{-1} (\boldsymbol{\varphi} - \boldsymbol{\mu}_\varphi) \quad (22)$$

$$= C + \log \mathcal{L}_{1,c}(\mu, \boldsymbol{\beta}, \boldsymbol{\nu}_1, \psi) + \log \mathcal{L}_{2,c}(\boldsymbol{\nu}_1) + \log \mathcal{L}_{3,c}(\omega) + \log \mathcal{L}_{4,c}(\psi) \quad (23)$$

where C is a constant, $\|\cdot\|_2^2$ denotes the squared L²-norm.

The EM algorithm consists of two major steps, one for expectation (E-step) and one for maximisation (M-step), see [McLachlan and Krishnan \(2007\)](#). At the $(m+1)$ -th iteration the EM algorithm proceeds as follows:

- (i) **E-step:** computes the conditional expectation of the complete-data log-likelihood (18) given the observed data $\{y_t, \mathbf{x}_t\}_{t=1}^T$ and the m -th iteration parameters updates $\widehat{\boldsymbol{\vartheta}}^{(m)}$

$$\mathcal{Q}\left(\boldsymbol{\vartheta}, \widehat{\boldsymbol{\vartheta}}^{(m)}\right) = \mathbb{E}_{\widehat{\boldsymbol{\vartheta}}^{(m)}} \left[\log \mathcal{L}_c(\boldsymbol{\vartheta}) \mid \{y_t, \mathbf{x}_t\}_{t=1}^T \right]; \quad (24)$$

- (ii) **M-step:** choose $\widehat{\boldsymbol{\vartheta}}^{(m)}$ by maximising (24) with respect to $\boldsymbol{\vartheta}$

$$\widehat{\boldsymbol{\vartheta}}^{(m)} = \arg \max_{\boldsymbol{\vartheta}} \mathcal{Q}\left(\boldsymbol{\vartheta}, \widehat{\boldsymbol{\vartheta}}^{(m)}\right). \quad (25)$$

Ignoring constant terms, the objective function of the EM algorithm becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{Q}(\boldsymbol{\vartheta} | \widehat{\boldsymbol{\vartheta}}^{(m)}) &= -\frac{T}{2} \log(2\pi) - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{t=1}^T \log(h_t) - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{t=1}^T \frac{\|y_t - \mu - \mathbf{x}_t' \boldsymbol{\beta} - \mathbf{z}_t' \boldsymbol{\varphi}\|_2^2}{h_t} \\ &\quad - \frac{p}{2} \log(2\pi) - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=1}^p \mathbb{E}_\gamma(\log(b_j)) - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=1}^p \beta_j^2 \mathbb{E}_\gamma\left(\frac{1}{b_j}\right) \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\quad + \sum_{j=1}^p \mathbb{E}_\gamma(\gamma_j) \log\left(\frac{\omega}{1-\omega}\right) + (p+b-1) \log(1-\omega) + (a-1) \log(\omega) \\ &\quad - (a+b+2) \sum_{j=1}^p \log(1+\nu_{1,j}) + b \sum_{j=1}^p \log(\nu_{1,j}) - \sum_{j=1}^p \log(\text{Be}(a+1, b+1)) \\ &\quad - \log(\text{Be}(a, b)) - \frac{1}{2} \log(2\pi) - \frac{1}{2} \log(\sigma_\gamma^2) - \frac{1}{2} \frac{(\gamma_h - \mu_\gamma)^2}{\sigma_\gamma^2} \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

$$- \frac{1}{2} \log(2\pi) - \frac{1}{2} \log(\sigma_\alpha^2) - \frac{1}{2} \frac{(\alpha_h - \mu_\alpha)^2}{\sigma_\alpha^2} \quad (28)$$

$$- \frac{1}{2} \log(2\pi) - \frac{1}{2} \log(\sigma_\beta^2) - \frac{1}{2} \frac{(\beta_h - \mu_\beta)^2}{\sigma_\beta^2} \quad (29)$$

$$- \frac{1}{2} (\boldsymbol{\varphi} - \boldsymbol{\mu}_\varphi)' \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_\varphi^{-1} (\boldsymbol{\varphi} - \boldsymbol{\mu}_\varphi) \quad (30)$$

$$= C + \mathcal{Q}_{1,c}(\boldsymbol{\mu}, \boldsymbol{\beta}, \boldsymbol{\nu}_1, \psi) + \mathcal{Q}_{2,c}(\boldsymbol{\nu}_1) + \mathcal{Q}_{3,c}(\omega) + \mathcal{Q}_{4,c}(\psi), \quad (31)$$

where

$$C = -\frac{T+p+f}{2} \log(2\pi) - \log(\text{Be}(a+1, b+1)) - \sum_{j=1}^p \log(\text{Be}(a, b)) - \frac{1}{2} \log |\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_\varphi| \quad (32)$$

$$\mathcal{Q}_{1,c}(\mu, \boldsymbol{\beta}, \boldsymbol{\varphi}, \nu_1) = -\frac{1}{2} \sum_{t=1}^T \log(h_t) - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{t=1}^T \frac{\|y_t - \mu - \mathbf{x}'_t \boldsymbol{\beta} - \mathbf{z}'_t \boldsymbol{\varphi}\|_2^2}{h_t} - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=1}^p \beta_j^2 \widehat{b_j^{-1}}^{(m)} \quad (33)$$

$$\mathcal{Q}_{2,c}(\nu_1) = -\frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=1}^p \widehat{\log(b_j)}^{(m)} - (a+b+2) \sum_{j=1}^p \log(1 + \nu_{1,j}) + b \sum_{j=1}^p \log(\nu_{1,j}) \quad (34)$$

$$\mathcal{Q}_{3,c}(\omega) = \sum_{j=1}^p \widehat{\gamma_j}^{(m)} \log\left(\frac{\omega}{1-\omega}\right) + (p+b-1) \log(1-\omega) + (a-1) \log(\omega) \quad (35)$$

$$\mathcal{Q}_{4,c}(\psi) = -\frac{1}{2} \frac{(\gamma_h - \mu_\gamma)^2}{\sigma_\gamma^2} - \frac{1}{2} \frac{(\alpha_h - \mu_\alpha)^2}{\sigma_\alpha^2} - \frac{1}{2} \frac{(\beta_h - \mu_\beta)^2}{\sigma_\beta^2}$$

$$\mathcal{Q}_{5,c}(\boldsymbol{\varphi}) = -\frac{1}{2} (\boldsymbol{\varphi} - \boldsymbol{\mu}_\varphi)' \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_\varphi^{-1} (\boldsymbol{\varphi} - \boldsymbol{\mu}_\varphi), \quad (36)$$

and

$$\widehat{\gamma_j}^{(m)} = \mathbf{E}_\gamma(\gamma_j | \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{X}, \widehat{\boldsymbol{\vartheta}}^{(m)}) \quad (37)$$

$$\widehat{b_j^{-1}}^{(m)} = \mathbf{E}_\gamma\left(\frac{1}{b_j} | \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{X}, \widehat{\boldsymbol{\vartheta}}^{(m)}\right) \quad (38)$$

$$\widehat{\log(b_j)}^{(m)} = \mathbf{E}_\gamma(\log(b_j) | \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{X}, \widehat{\boldsymbol{\vartheta}}^{(m)}), \quad (39)$$

for $j = 1, 2, \dots, p$. As concerns the first expected value we have

$$\widehat{\gamma_j}^{(m)} = \mathbf{E}_\gamma(\gamma_j | \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{X}, \widehat{\boldsymbol{\vartheta}}^{(m)}) \quad (40)$$

$$= \mathbf{P}(\gamma_j = 1 | \widehat{\boldsymbol{\vartheta}}^{(m)}) \quad (41)$$

$$= \frac{\phi(\widehat{\beta_j}^{(m)} | \gamma_j = 1) \mathbf{P}(\gamma_j = 1 | \omega)}{\phi(\widehat{\beta_j}^{(m)} | \gamma_j = 1) \mathbf{P}(\gamma_j = 1 | \omega) + \phi(\widehat{\beta_j}^{(m)} | \gamma_j = 0) \mathbf{P}(\gamma_j = 0 | \omega)} \quad (42)$$

$$= \frac{1}{1 + \widehat{d_j}^{(m)}}, \quad (43)$$

where $\widehat{d}_j^{(m)} = \sqrt{\frac{\widehat{\nu}_{1,j}^{(m)}}{\nu_0}} \exp \left\{ \frac{(\widehat{\beta}_j^{(m)})^2}{2} \left(\frac{1}{\widehat{\nu}_{i,j}^{(m)}} - \frac{1}{\nu_0} \right) \right\} \frac{1 - \widehat{\omega}^{(m)}}{\widehat{\omega}^{(m)}}$, while the second and third expectations become

$$\widehat{b}_j^{-1(m)} = \mathbb{E}_\gamma \left(\frac{1}{b_j} \mid \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{X}, \widehat{\boldsymbol{\vartheta}}^{(m)} \right) \quad (44)$$

$$= \frac{1}{\nu_{1,j}} \widehat{\gamma}_j^{(m)} + \frac{1}{\nu_0} \left(1 - \widehat{\gamma}_j^{(m)} \right) \quad (45)$$

$$\widehat{\log(b_j)}^{(m)} = \mathbb{E}_\gamma \left(\log(b_j) \mid \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{X}, \widehat{\boldsymbol{\vartheta}}^{(m)} \right), \quad (46)$$

$$= \log(\nu_{1,j}) \widehat{\gamma}_j^{(m)} + \log(\nu_0) \left(1 - \widehat{\gamma}_j^{(m)} \right). \quad (47)$$

One nice feature of the EM algorithms would be the analytical solution of the M-step for all the parameters. Unfortunately, for the Gaussian regression model with ℓ_1 spike-and-slab here considered, a closed form update does not exist for all the parameters. Therefore, we resort to a Conditional Expectation Maximisation (CEM) approach, see [McLachlan and Krishnan \(2007\)](#). Under the Spike-and-Slab prior in equation (10), an iteration of the CEM algorithm cycles through the set of all the model parameters. Specifically, we get

$$\widehat{\boldsymbol{\vartheta}}_\star^{(m+1)} = \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\vartheta_\star} + \mathbf{K}_\star (\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{X}_\star \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\vartheta_\star}) \quad (48)$$

$$\mathbf{K}_\star = \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\vartheta_\star} \mathbf{X}_\star' \mathbf{F}^{-1} \quad (49)$$

$$\mathbf{F} = \mathbf{H}^{(m)-1} + \mathbf{X}_\star \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\vartheta_\star} \mathbf{X}_\star' \quad (50)$$

$$\widehat{\omega}^{(m+1)} = \frac{1}{p + b + a - 2} \left(\sum_{j=1}^p \gamma_j^{(m)} + a - 1 \right) \quad (51)$$

$$\widehat{\nu}_1^{(m+1)} = \frac{-(A + B + b) - \Delta}{2(B - a - 2)} \quad (52)$$

$$\Delta = \sqrt{(A + B + b)^2 - 4(B - a - 2)A} \quad (53)$$

$$B = -\frac{\widehat{\gamma}^{(m)}}{2} \quad (54)$$

$$A = \frac{1}{2} \widehat{\beta}^{(m+1)2} \odot \widehat{\gamma}^{(m)}, \quad (55)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\vartheta}_\star = (\mu, \boldsymbol{\beta}', \boldsymbol{\varphi}')'$, $\mathbf{y} = (y_1, y_2, \dots, y_T)'$, $\mathbf{X}_\star = (\boldsymbol{\iota}_T \quad \mathbf{X} \quad \mathbf{Z})$, $\boldsymbol{\iota}_T$ is a column vector of dimension $(T \times 1)$ of unit elements, $\mathbf{X} = (\mathbf{x}'_1, \mathbf{x}'_2, \dots, \mathbf{x}'_T)'$ and $\mathbf{Z} = (\mathbf{z}'_1, \mathbf{z}'_2, \dots, \mathbf{z}'_T)'$, $\boldsymbol{\mu}_{\vartheta_\star} = (\mu_\mu, \boldsymbol{\theta}', \boldsymbol{\mu}'_\varphi)'$, $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\vartheta_\star} = \text{diag}(\sigma_\mu^2, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_\beta, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_\varphi)$, \odot denote the Hadamart componentwise vector multiplication, $\mathbf{D}^{(m)} = \text{diag} \left\{ \widehat{b}_1^{-1(m)}, \widehat{b}_2^{-1(m)}, \dots, \widehat{b}_p^{-1(m)} \right\}$ and $\mathbf{H}^{(m)} = \text{diag} \left\{ \widehat{h}_1^{(m)}, \widehat{h}_2^{(m)}, \dots, \widehat{h}_T^{(m)} \right\}$. A detailed proof of the updating equations (48)–(50) is provided in [Appendix A.1](#), while a

detailed proof of the updating equations (52)–(55) is provided in equation A.2.

3.4 Dealing with the GARCH parameters

The GARCH parameters $(\gamma_h, \alpha_h, \beta_h)$ do not admit a known closed form expression for the maximum of the log-likelihood because of the recursive nature of the variance equation in model (8). Therefore, we propose an approximate EM algorithm where the full conditionals of $(\gamma_h, \alpha_h, \beta_h)$ are approximated by a simpler model as in [Ardia \(2008\)](#) that introduced a similar approach in order to tailor the Metropolis–Hastings (MH) proposal to the target. As a further reference for an approximate EM within the context of multivariate GARCH models, see [Demos and Sentana \(1998\)](#).

The approximating densities for the GARCH parameters are obtained by exploiting the well known ARMA representation of GARCH processes for $\varepsilon_t^2 = y_t - \mu - \mathbf{x}_t' \boldsymbol{\beta}$, for $t = 1, 2, \dots, T$. Indeed, by defining the martingale difference process $v_t = \varepsilon_t^2 - \mathbb{E}_{t-1}(\varepsilon_t^2) = \left(\frac{\varepsilon_t^2}{h_t} - 1\right) h_t \sim (\chi_1^2 - 1) h_t$ with $\mathbb{E}(v_t | h_t) = 0$ and $\mathbb{E}(v_t^2 | h_t) = 2h_t^2$, we get the following stationary ARMA representation for the squared innovations ε_t^2

$$\varepsilon_t^2 = \gamma_h + (\alpha_h + \beta_h) \varepsilon_{t-1}^2 - \beta_h v_{t-1} + v_t, \quad (56)$$

for $t = 1, 2, \dots, T$. Following [Ardia \(2008\)](#), expression (56) can be written as $v_t = \varepsilon_t^2 - \ell_t^{*'} \tilde{\psi}_h$ where $\ell_t^* = (l_t^*, v_t^*)'$ and $\tilde{\psi}_h = (\gamma_h, \alpha_h)'$, with

$$l_t^* = 1 + \beta l_{t-1}^* \quad (57)$$

$$v_t^* = v_{t-1} + \beta v_{t-1}^*, \quad (58)$$

where $l_0^* = v_0^* = 0$. The function v_t in equation (56) can therefore be expressed as a linear function of the vector of transformed parameters $\tilde{\psi}_h$. The procedure then approximates the innovation term v_t in equation (56) by a Gaussian distribution $z_t \sim \mathbf{N}(0, 2h_t^2)$ leading to the following auxiliary model

$$z_t(\psi) = \varepsilon_t^2 - \gamma_h - (\alpha_h + \beta_h) \varepsilon_{t-1}^2 + \beta_h z_{t-1}(\psi), \quad (59)$$

where $z_t(\psi) = \varepsilon_t^2 - \ell_t^{*'} \tilde{\psi}_h$, $\mathbf{z} = \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^2 - \mathbf{L} \tilde{\psi}_h$, $\mathbf{L} = (\ell_1', \ell_2', \dots, \ell_T)'$ and $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^2 = (\varepsilon_1^2, \varepsilon_2^2, \dots, \varepsilon_T^2)'$. Therefore, we can approximate the full conditional distribution of the GARCH parameters ψ

using the following the auxiliary model

$$\mathcal{L}^*(\gamma_h, \alpha_h | \mathbf{y}) \propto |\mathbf{\Lambda}|^{-\frac{1}{2}} \exp \left\{ -\frac{1}{2} \mathbf{z}' \mathbf{\Lambda}^{-1} \mathbf{z} \right\} \mathbb{1}_{\mathcal{S}}(\tilde{\psi}_h), \quad (60)$$

where $\mathbf{\Lambda} = \mathbf{\Lambda}(\psi) = \text{diag}(\{2h_t^2(\psi)\}_{t=1}^T)$ and \mathcal{S} denotes the convex region such that $\gamma_h \geq 0$, $\alpha_h > 0$. The approximating density for γ_h, α_h is obtained by combining the approximated likelihood function defined in equation (60) and the prior density defined in equation , by the usual Bayesian updating

$$\pi(\tilde{\psi}_h | \beta_h, \mathbf{y}) \propto \phi(\tilde{\psi}_h | \hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_{\tilde{\psi}_h}, \hat{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_{\tilde{\psi}_h}) \mathbb{1}_{(\mathcal{S})}(\tilde{\psi}_h), \quad (61)$$

where

$$\hat{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_{\tilde{\psi}_h} = (\mathbf{L}' \mathbf{\Lambda}^{-1} \mathbf{L} + \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\tilde{\psi}_h}^{-1})^{-1} \quad (62)$$

$$\hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_{\tilde{\psi}_h} = \hat{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_{\tilde{\psi}_h} (\mathbf{L}' \mathbf{\Lambda}^{-1} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} + \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\tilde{\psi}_h}^{-1} \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\tilde{\psi}_h}). \quad (63)$$

The function $z_t(\psi)$ in equation (59) cannot be expressed as a linear function of the parameter β_h . To overcome this problem, we linearise $z_t(\psi)$ with respect to β_h by a first order Taylor expansion at point $\hat{\beta}_h^{(k-1)}$

$$z_t(\beta) \approx z_t(\hat{\beta}_h^{(k-1)}) - \nabla_t^{\hat{\beta}_h^{(k-1)}} (\beta - \hat{\beta}_h^{(k-1)}), \quad (64)$$

where $\nabla_t^{\hat{\beta}_h^{(k-1)}} = -\frac{\partial z_t(\beta)}{\partial \beta} \Big|_{\beta=\hat{\beta}_h^{(k-1)}}$ where $\hat{\beta}_h^{(k-1)}$ is the value of the parameter β in the previous iteration of the EM algorithm and the term $\nabla_t^{\hat{\beta}_h^{(k-1)}}$ can be calculated by the following recursion

$$\nabla_t^{\hat{\beta}_h^{(k-1)}} = \varepsilon_{t-1}^2 - z_{t-1}(\hat{\beta}_h^{(k-1)}) + \hat{\beta}_h^{(k-1)} \nabla_{t-1}^{\hat{\beta}_h^{(k-1)}}, \quad (65)$$

with $\nabla_0^{\hat{\beta}_h^{(k-1)}} = 0$. Furthermore, let $r_t(\hat{\beta}_h^{(k-1)}) = z_t(\hat{\beta}_h^{(k-1)}) + \hat{\beta}_h^{(k-1)} \nabla_t^{\hat{\beta}_h^{(k-1)}}$ and $z_t(\hat{\beta}_h^{(k-1)}) = r_t(\hat{\beta}_h^{(k-1)}) - \hat{\beta}_h^{(k-1)} \nabla_t^{\hat{\beta}_h^{(k-1)}}$, then the main term in the quadratic form in equation (60) can be expressed as $\mathbf{z} = \mathbf{r} - \beta_h \nabla_{\beta}$, where $\nabla_{\beta} = (\nabla_1, \nabla_2, \dots, \nabla_T)'$ and $\mathbf{r} = (r_1(\hat{\beta}_h^{(k-1)}), r_2(\hat{\beta}_h^{(k-1)}), \dots, r_T(\hat{\beta}_h^{(k-1)}))'$ yielding the following approximation for the likelihood function of β_h

$$\mathcal{L}^*(\beta_h | \mathbf{Y}, \gamma_h, \alpha_h) \propto |\mathbf{\Lambda}|^{-\frac{1}{2}} \exp \left\{ -\frac{1}{2} (\mathbf{r} - \beta_h \nabla_{\beta})' \mathbf{\Lambda}^{-1} (\mathbf{r} - \beta_h \nabla_{\beta}) \right\} \mathbb{1}_{(0,1-\alpha_h)}(\beta_h), \quad (66)$$

The approximated full conditional distribution of the parameter β_h is obtained by combining the approximated likelihood function defined in equation (66) and the prior density defined in equation , by the usual Bayesian updating

$$\pi\left(\beta_h \mid \omega_h, \alpha_h, \widehat{\beta}_h^{(k-1)}, \mathbf{Y}\right) \propto \phi\left(\beta_h \mid \widehat{\mu}_\beta, \widehat{\sigma}_\beta^2\right) \mathbb{1}_{(0,1-\alpha_h)}(\beta_h), \quad (67)$$

where

$$\widehat{\sigma}_\beta^2 = \left(\nabla'_\beta \Lambda^{-1} \nabla_\beta + \frac{1}{\sigma_{\beta_h}^2}\right)^{-1} \quad (68)$$

$$\widehat{\mu}_\beta = \widehat{\sigma}_\beta^2 \left(\nabla'_\beta \Lambda^{-1} \mathbf{r} + \frac{\mu_{\beta_h}}{\sigma_{\beta_h}^2}\right). \quad (69)$$

4 Empirical Analysis

4.1 The data

We consider the weekly closing price series of 1248 world financial firms (banks, brokers insurances and other financial services) active and dead to deal with delisting in stocks markets, and therefore to avoid the survivorship bias (Shumway, 1997). The considered period goes from the 29th December 2000 to 6th October 2017.¹ We report the list of financial firms per country and category in Table 5 of Appendix B. The networks are estimated using a rolling window approach with length size of 104 weekly observations (≈ 2 years). Hence, we obtain a total of 772 estimated networks from 20th December 2002 to 29th September 2017.² Each windows contains the institutions with at least a number of observations equal to its size. Figure 1 reports the cardinality of the dataset over time with a minimum (maximum) of selected firms equal to X (Y). Therefore, we have time-varying dataset where the number of covariates are strictly larger then the number of observations.

4.2 Network estimates

We report in Figure 2 the cross-sectional distributions of the selected regressors for $c > 0.95$ (left panel) and the cross-sectional distribution for the estimated betas for the financial institutions in each period (right panel). At the first sight, the cross-sectional distribution of the selected

¹The data have been downloaded from Thomson Reuters Datastream.

²The estimations have been parallelized and implemented in Matlab on the LOEWE-CSC cluster using 100 cores. The computation has required approximatively 36 hours.

Figure 1: Cross-sectional sample size of the considered financial institutions over time.

regressors provides an indication about the incoming connection among the financial institutions in the system. Looking at the left panel, the cross-sectional dimension has an impact on the distributions at the beginning of the period as described by Figure 1. Interestingly, there is a shift on the cross-sectional distributions during the 2007 – 2009 period in occurrence of the Global financial crisis which could indicate a change in the network structure. In this regard, we report in Table 1 the descriptive statistics by year for the cross-sectional distributions of the selected regressors. The values for the mean are larger than the values of the median in all the considered period which suggests that the cross-sectional distributions are right-skewed (i.e., power tail). As shown graphically, there is a decline of the mean (first column) and the median (second column) during the global financial crisis, even if the latter is less pronounced than the previous. The maximum difference between the mean and the median is during 2009 – 2010 which indicates that the distribution is strongly right-skewed in the period. Conversely, the standard deviation (third column) increases of the 42% in 2007 indicating a greater dispersion about among the number of incoming connection. In the same manner, the quantile at 10% (fourth column) and the quantile at 90% (fifth column) show a widening of the distribution during the same period (2009 – 2010).

Finally, the right panel in Figure 2 shows a bimodal cross-sectional distribution for the betas indicating a mass concentration for positive and negative values. The values are reported in Table 2 and show that the mean, median and standard deviation are substantially stable during the considered period. As expected, this preliminary analysis shows a change of the connectedness of the financial network over time.

To better understand the network connectedness in terms of financial contagion, we focus on the outgoing linkages among the firms over time which play a crucial role in the description

Figure 2: Cross-sectional distribution of the selected regressors for $c > 0.95$ (left panel) and cross-sectional distribution for estimated betas (right panel) from 20th December 2002 to 29th September 2017. The color indicates the intensity of the frequency from blue to yellow (see the colormap).

	<i>mean</i>	<i>median</i>	σ	$q_{10\%}$	$q_{90\%}$
<i>2002</i>	18.01	17.00	8.23	12.50	21.50
<i>2003</i>	19.30	17.54	10.28	13.23	23.13
<i>2004</i>	21.51	18.82	12.35	14.57	25.79
<i>2005</i>	22.24	19.71	12.26	15.53	26.37
<i>2006</i>	21.08	19.16	10.22	15.11	24.78
<i>2007</i>	20.79	19.00	14.51	15.05	24.06
<i>2008</i>	20.20	17.96	11.00	14.02	24.03
<i>2009</i>	20.07	16.00	15.32	12.04	26.57
<i>2010</i>	21.86	17.00	17.03	12.85	32.93
<i>2011</i>	21.63	19.12	11.39	15.38	25.69
<i>2012</i>	20.50	19.21	8.40	15.32	23.96
<i>2013</i>	20.96	18.94	11.07	14.88	25.03
<i>2014</i>	21.23	18.96	12.06	14.94	25.26
<i>2015</i>	21.18	18.98	11.61	14.97	24.79
<i>2016</i>	20.60	18.47	11.11	14.64	24.02
<i>2017</i>	20.77	18.96	9.99	15.00	24.33

Table 1: Descriptive statistics reported by year for the cross-sectional distributions on the number of selected regressors.

of the network connectivity. The network out-degree measure is

$$d_{i,t}^{\text{out}} = \sum_{j=1}^{n_t} A_{ij,t},$$

where $A_{ij,t}$ is the element of the adjacency matrix (i.e., $\mathbb{1}_{\gamma_{i,j} > c}$) at time t . Figure 3 reports the out-degree distribution of the estimated networks over time. Similar to what discussed in the descriptive statistics on the regressors, the cross-sectional distributions appear to be right-skewed suggesting the presence of a majority of nodes having low degrees and a minority, also known as hubs, having high degrees. More in general, this is a well known property of large networks where the nodes connectivities follow a scale-free power-law distribution (Barabási and Albert, 1999), property that is present also in financial networks (Schweitzer et al., 2009). For example, interbank networks show the scale-free characteristic with the presence of nodes acting as hubs (Iori et al., 2008; Boss et al., 2004). The analysis of the changes in the shape of the out-degree distribution over time can provide insights about the change of connectedness for the financial firms in the network. In fact, an increase in the shape of the distribution could indicate an increase of the number of nodes with higher out-degree (new hubs), a further increase in the outgoing connection of existing hubs or both. Therefore, we analyse the shape of the out-degree distributions using the Generalized Pareto Distribution (Pickands III, 1975) which is particular suitable for the heavy-tailed case.

The cumulative density function of the Generalized Pareto distribution is

$$F_{x,\xi,\beta} = \begin{cases} 1 - \left(1 + \xi \frac{x}{\beta}\right)^{-1/\xi} & \text{if } \xi \neq 0, \beta > 0, \\ 1 - e^{-x/\beta} & \text{if } \xi = 0, \beta > 0. \end{cases}$$

where

$$\begin{cases} x \geq 0 & \text{if } \xi \geq 0, \\ 0 \leq x \leq -\beta/\xi & \text{if } \xi < 0. \end{cases}$$

and β and ξ are scale and shape parameters, respectively. If $\xi = 0$, the GPD distribution reduces to the exponential distribution with mean β . For further details, see for example Castillo and Hadi (1997) and Embrechts et al. (2013). We estimate the GPD on the out-degree distribution over time and hence, obtain a time-sequence for the values $\hat{\xi}_t$ and $\hat{\beta}_t$. For ease of reference, we call $\hat{\beta}_t$ as the hubs indicator and report it in Figure 4.³ Clearly, the series shows an interesting dynamic with occasional level shifts over the period contingent on the occurrence of particular

³We have checked that the condition $0 \leq x \leq -\beta/\xi$ is met for negative values of $\hat{\xi}_t$. Moreover, we test that the time-varying cross-sectional sample size does not affect its dynamic by performing a regression on levels and differences.

	<i>mean</i>	<i>median</i>	σ		<i>mean</i>	<i>median</i>	σ
<i>2002</i>	-0.1521	-0.1475	0.0711	<i>2010</i>	-0.1391	-0.1337	0.0787
	0.1462	0.1400	0.0674	<i>2010</i>	0.1408	0.1341	0.0762
<i>2003</i>	-0.1477	-0.1427	0.0727	<i>2011</i>	-0.1430	-0.1381	0.0717
	0.1431	0.1377	0.0682	<i>2011</i>	0.1492	0.1445	0.0715
<i>2004</i>	-0.1404	-0.1357	0.0716	<i>2012</i>	-0.1539	-0.1486	0.0727
	0.1396	0.1347	0.0679	<i>2012</i>	0.1571	0.1517	0.0718
<i>2005</i>	-0.1358	-0.1311	0.0693	<i>2013</i>	-0.1452	-0.1403	0.0726
	0.1371	0.1320	0.0666	<i>2013</i>	0.1431	0.1380	0.0684
<i>2006</i>	-0.1406	-0.1355	0.0684	<i>2014</i>	-0.1367	-0.1328	0.0691
	0.1418	0.1365	0.0660	<i>2014</i>	0.1363	0.1315	0.0657
<i>2007</i>	-0.1425	-0.1373	0.0679	<i>2015</i>	-0.1373	-0.1326	0.0692
	0.1521	0.1466	0.0690	<i>2015</i>	0.1405	0.1359	0.0678
<i>2008</i>	-0.1512	-0.1469	0.0742	<i>2016</i>	-0.1432	-0.1382	0.0709
	0.1543	0.1497	0.0738	<i>2016</i>	0.1472	0.1418	0.0710
<i>2009</i>	-0.1509	-0.1476	0.0808	<i>2017</i>	-0.1447	-0.1400	0.0709
	0.1513	0.1463	0.0788	<i>2017</i>	0.1488	0.1431	0.0715

Table 2: Descriptive statistics reported by year for the Cross-sectional distributions on the betas of the selected regressors.

Figure 3: Cross-sectional out-degree distribution of the considered financial institutions over time.

Figure 4: The estimated shape parameter $\hat{\xi}_t$ (the hubs indicator) for the out-degree distribution over time with the confidence interval at 95%. Red vertical lines indicate financial and economic events (see Table 3).

financial and economic events. Regarding the Global financial crisis and the European sovereign debt crisis, we identify and report the more relevant events in Table 3 plus two more recent episodes that have influenced the global market. Similar to contemporaneous financial stress indicators such as St. Louis Fed Financial Stress Index (STLFSI [Kliesen et al., 2010](#)) and CISS ([Hollo et al., 2012](#)), the hubs indicator is very reactive to stress events but, unlike those, is a simple estimates of the shape of the out-degree distribution and is not an aggregation of different sources. Obviously, other network measures can be implemented in the analysis. At the node level, eigenvector centrality which measures the influence of a node in the network. We leave this aspect and other measures for further research.

Moreover, we measure if the changes in the shape of the out-degree distribution provide an additional information content as predictor at the market level. We select as proxy for our reference market the MSCI World Financials index which captures large and mid cap representation across 23 developed countries and is consistent with our dataset.⁴ In this regard, we model the market returns as a function of the usual market drivers (i.e. volatility and risk premia) plus the hubs indicator. Hence, we consider the EGARCH-m model which take into account asymmetry in the volatility,

$$r_t = c + \sum_{l=1}^L \phi_l r_{t-l} + \sum_{m=0}^M \delta_m h_{t-m}^{1/2} + \sum_{k=0}^K \beta_k \Delta \xi_{t-k} + h_t^{1/2} z_t,$$

$$\log(h_t) = \omega + \sum_{i=1}^q g(z_{t-i}) + \sum_{j=1}^p \phi_j \log(h_{t-i}),$$

where $g(z_t) = \alpha z_t + \kappa [|z_t| - E|z_t|]$ and $\Delta \xi_{t-k}$ represents the changes in the hub indicator included in the mean equation. We estimate the AR(1)-EGARCH-m(1,1), a common choice in the empirical literature, and include $\Delta \xi_{t-k}$ up to the sixth lag to check its dynamic effects. The results are reported in Table 4 for the mean and volatility equations. By selecting a confidence level at 5%, the autoregressive term r_{t-1} and the lagged (log) volatility $\log(h_{t-i})$ in the mean equation do not have any impact on the dynamic of the market returns while, as expected, all the terms in the volatility have an impact on the market returns. We observe that the hubs-indicator has an impact on the market returns at the first and the forth lags. In particular, the coefficient of $\Delta \xi_{t-1}$ is -0.1474 and indicates that an increase of the hubs-indicator has a negative impact on the market returns. Interestingly, the hubs-indicator at the forth lag, $\Delta \xi_{t-4}$, shows a positive impact on the market returns representing a monthly effect (4 weeks). We interpret the weekly

⁴The MSCI World Financial index contains 23 developed countries for 3 main areas: i) *Americas*: Canada, United States; ii) *Europe&Middle East*: Austria, Belgium, Denmark, Finland, Germany, Ireland, Israel, Italy, Netherlands, Norway, Portugal, Spain Sweden, Switzerland, United Kingdom; iii) *Pacific*: Australia, Hong Kong, Japan, New Zealand and Singapore. These countries represent more than the 62% of our dataset.

<i>date</i>	<i>Event</i>	<i>Note</i>
10 May 2006	Fed 16th consecutive raise of interest rates	Inflation pressure with concerns for global economic growth.
29 June 2006	Fed 17th consecutive raise of interest rates	
17 February 2007	HSBC announces losses due to US subprime mortgage	Signal of vulnerability on subprime mortgages.
16 July 2007	Bear Stearns' two subprime HFs lost almost all the cap.	
15 September 2008	Bankruptcy of Lehman Brothers	Subprime financial crisis.
28 November 2010	Ireland bailout	European Sovereign debt crisis.
21 July 2011	Greece second bailout	
01 July 2013	30-Year Treasury Swaps Spread returns positive	Measure of the cost of funding. Signal of market normalization.
18 December 2015	Crude oil prices fall	WTI futures fell at \$36.66 per barrel.
15 July 2017	Global growth	Signals of continued and synchronized global growth.

Table 3: List of Financial and Economic events before and during the Global Financial crisis and the European Sovereign debt crisis.

and monthly effect similarly to the case of asymmetric propagation of volatility (Müller et al., 1997; Corsi, 2009) where actions of heterogeneous market participants affect the short and long time horizons. Therefore, the negative sign may reflect the asymmetric impact of the monthly participant component with respect to the weekly one, resulting in a mean reverting effect.

	estimate	s.e.	t-stat	p-value
<i>mean equation</i>				
(constant)	0.0010	0.0010	1.0000	0.3170
r_{t-1}	-0.0352	0.0402	-0.8800	0.3810
$\log(h_{t-1})$	0.3697	1.5314	0.2400	0.8090
$\Delta\xi_{t-1}$	-0.1475	0.0333	-4.4300	0.0000
$\Delta\xi_{t-2}$	-0.0948	0.0505	-1.8800	0.0600
$\Delta\xi_{t-3}$	-0.0282	0.0446	-0.6300	0.5270
$\Delta\xi_{t-4}$	0.1115	0.0466	2.3900	0.0170
$\Delta\xi_{t-5}$	0.0326	0.0445	0.7300	0.4630
$\Delta\xi_{t-6}$	-0.0045	0.0430	-0.1000	0.9170
<i>volatility equation</i>				
(constant)	-0.1540	0.0482	-3.2000	0.0010
z_{t-1}	-0.1363	0.0138	-9.8700	0.0000
$ z_{t-1} - E z_{t-1} $	0.0667	0.0228	2.9300	0.0030
$\log(h_{t-1})$	0.9798	0.0064	152.0000	0.0000
obs	765		Wald $\chi^2(5)$	29.25
Log-likelihood	1779.78		Prob $> \chi^2$	0.0003

Table 4: Estimates for the AR(1)-EGARCH-m(1,1) model by including the (lagged) changes in the hubs indicator $\Delta\xi_t$ in the mean equation.

To check if the hubs-indicator maintain its explanatory power on the market returns, we perform a further regression by including other three set of predictors: i) changes in volatility indices for four macro-area which are representative of the global market index; ii) changes in financial stress indicators such as the CISS and the STLFSI and iii) the Fama and French 5 factors (Fama and French, 2015).⁵ Results are included in Appendix C and confirm the predictive ability of the hubs indicator in all the regressions.

⁵Data source (in parenthesis): CISS(ECB-sdw), STLFSI (FRED-St.Louis Fed), Volatility indices (Bloomberg), Fama and French 5 factors (French's website).

5 Conclusion

This paper focuses on the problem of variable selection and shrinkage in high dimensional sparse regression models where the regularisation method is an extension of a previous LASSO models. The model allows to include a large number of institutions which improves the identification of the relationship and maintains at the same time the flexibility of the univariate framework where the conditional distribution of the error term follows ARCH-type process. The extraction methodology identifies a weighted directed network where the adjacency matrix is built "row by row" and the weight of each linkages for one institution is defined by the posterior inclusion probability of the other institutions in the system. Findings show that changes in the shape of the out-degree distribution of the network over time represent a reactive financial stress indicator of the global financial system and a significant predictor of market returns.

Algorithm 1 Heteroskedastic Stochastic Search Variable Selection EM

Given the value of the parameters at the m -th iteration, $\widehat{\boldsymbol{\vartheta}}^{(m)}$ as well as the values of the conditional variances $\left\{\widehat{h}_t^{(m)}\right\}_{t=1}^T$, the next iteration of the SSVS-EM algorithm update the parameters as follows:

1. update the inclusion indicators: $\widehat{\gamma}_j^{(m+1)} = \frac{1}{1+\widehat{d}_j^{(m+1)}}$, where

$$\widehat{d}_j^{(m+1)} = \sqrt{\frac{\widehat{\nu}_{1,j}^{(m)}}{\nu_0}} \exp \left\{ \frac{\left(\widehat{\beta}_j^m\right)^2}{2} \left(\frac{1}{\widehat{\nu}_{i,j}^{(m)}} - \frac{1}{\nu_0} \right) \right\} \frac{1 - \widehat{\omega}^{(m)}}{\widehat{\omega}^{(m)}},$$

for $j = 1, 2, \dots, p$;

2. update the latent factors:

$$\begin{aligned} \widehat{b}_j^{-1(m+1)} &= \frac{1}{\nu_{1,j}} \widehat{\gamma}_j^{(m+1)} + \frac{1}{\nu_0} \left(1 - \widehat{\gamma}_j^{(m+1)}\right) \\ \widehat{\log(b_j)}^{(m+1)} &= \log(\nu_{1,j}) \widehat{\gamma}_j^{(m+1)} + \log(\nu_0) \left(1 - \widehat{\gamma}_j^{(m+1)}\right), \end{aligned}$$

3. update the regression parameters $\boldsymbol{\vartheta}_* = (\boldsymbol{\mu}, \boldsymbol{\beta}', \boldsymbol{\varphi}')'$:

$$\begin{aligned} \widehat{\boldsymbol{\vartheta}}_*^{(m+1)} &= \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\vartheta_*} + \mathbf{K}_* (\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{X}_* \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\vartheta_*}) \\ \widehat{\omega}^{(m+1)} &= \frac{1}{p + b + a - 2} \left(\sum_{j=1}^p \gamma_j^{(m+1)} + a - 1 \right) \\ \widehat{\nu}_1^{(m+1)} &= \frac{-(A + B + b) - \Delta}{2(B - a - 2)}, \end{aligned}$$

where $\mathbf{K}_* = \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\vartheta_*} \mathbf{X}_*' \mathbf{F}^{-1}$, $\mathbf{F} = \mathbf{H}^{(m)-1} + \mathbf{X}_* \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\vartheta_*} \mathbf{X}_*'$,

$\Delta = \sqrt{(A + B + b)^2 - 4(B - a - 2)A}$, $B = -\frac{\widehat{\gamma}^{(m+1)}}{2}$, $A = \frac{1}{2} \widehat{\beta}^{(m+1)^2} \odot \widehat{\gamma}^{(m+1)}$, \odot denote the Hadamart componentwise vector multiplication,

$\mathbf{D}^{(m+1)} = \text{diag} \left\{ \widehat{b}_1^{-1(m+1)}, \widehat{b}_2^{-1(m+1)}, \dots, \widehat{b}_p^{-1(m+1)} \right\}$ and

$\mathbf{H}^{(m)} = \text{diag} \left\{ \widehat{h}_1^{(m)}, \widehat{h}_2^{(m)}, \dots, \widehat{h}_T^{(m)} \right\}$;

4. update the GARCH parameters: $\widehat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_{\widetilde{\psi}_h} = \widehat{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_{\widetilde{\psi}_h} \left(\mathbf{L}' \boldsymbol{\Lambda}^{-1} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} + \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\widetilde{\psi}_h}^{-1} \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\widetilde{\psi}_h} \right)$ and

$$\widehat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_{\beta} = \widehat{\sigma}_{\beta}^2 \left(\boldsymbol{\nabla}'_{\beta} \boldsymbol{\Lambda}^{-1} \mathbf{r} + \frac{\boldsymbol{\mu}_{\beta h}}{\sigma_{\beta h}^2} \right).$$

A Additional results

A.1 Update of ϑ_*

Let $\mathcal{Q}_{\vartheta_*,c}(\mu, \beta, \varphi) = \mathcal{Q}_{6,c}(\mu, \beta, \varphi) + \mathcal{Q}_{7,c}(\varphi) + \mathcal{Q}_{8,c}(\mu)$ be the objective function with respect to the parameters $\vartheta_* = (\mu, \beta', \varphi)'$, where

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{Q}_{6,c}(\mu, \beta, \varphi) &= -\frac{1}{2} \sum_{t=1}^T \frac{\|y_t - \mu - \mathbf{x}'_t \beta - \mathbf{z}'_t \varphi\|_2^2}{h_t} - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=1}^p \beta_j^2 \widehat{b_j^{-1}}^{(m)} \\ \mathcal{Q}_{7,c}(\varphi) &= -\frac{1}{2} (\varphi - \boldsymbol{\mu}_\varphi)' \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_\varphi^{-1} (\varphi - \boldsymbol{\mu}_\varphi) \\ \mathcal{Q}_{8,c}(\mu) &= -\frac{1}{2} \frac{(\mu - \mu_\mu)^2}{\sigma_\mu^2}.\end{aligned}$$

Upon defining the quantities $\mathbf{y} = (y_1, y_2, \dots, y_T)'$, $\mathbf{X}_* = \begin{pmatrix} \boldsymbol{\nu}_T & \mathbf{X} & \mathbf{Z} \end{pmatrix}$, where $\boldsymbol{\nu}_T$ is a column vector of dimension $(T \times 1)$, $\mathbf{X} = (\mathbf{x}'_1, \mathbf{x}'_2, \dots, \mathbf{x}'_T)'$ and $\mathbf{Z} = (\mathbf{z}'_1, \mathbf{z}'_2, \dots, \mathbf{z}'_T)'$, $\boldsymbol{\mu}_{\vartheta_*} = (\mu_\mu, \mathbf{0}', \boldsymbol{\mu}'_\varphi)'$, $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\vartheta_*} = \text{diag}(\sigma_\mu^2, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_\beta, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_\varphi)$ the objective function $\mathcal{Q}_{\vartheta_*,c}(\mu, \beta, \varphi)$ can be rewritten as

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{Q}_{\vartheta_*,c}(\mu, \beta, \varphi) &= -\frac{1}{2} (\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{X}_* \vartheta_*)' \mathbf{H}^{(m)-1} (\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{X}_* \vartheta_*) \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{2} (\vartheta_* - \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\vartheta_*})' \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\vartheta_*}^{-1} (\vartheta_* - \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\vartheta_*}),\end{aligned}\tag{70}$$

thereby leading to the following first order condition with respect to the vector of unknown parameters ϑ_*

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{Q}_{\vartheta_*,c}(\mu, \beta, \varphi)}{\partial \vartheta_*} = -\mathbf{X}'_* \mathbf{H}^{(m)-1} \mathbf{X}_* \vartheta_* + \mathbf{X}'_* \mathbf{H}^{(m)-1} \mathbf{y} - \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\vartheta_*}^{-1} \vartheta_* + \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\vartheta_*}^{-1} \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\vartheta_*} = 0,\tag{71}$$

and to the parameter update $\widehat{\vartheta}_*^{(m+1)} = \left(\mathbf{X}'_* \mathbf{H}^{(m)-1} \mathbf{X}_* + \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\vartheta_*}^{-1} \right)^{-1} \left(\mathbf{X}'_* \mathbf{H}^{(m)-1} \mathbf{y} + \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\vartheta_*}^{-1} \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\vartheta_*} \right)$. After some manipulations, we get

$$\begin{aligned}\left(\mathbf{X}'_* \mathbf{H}^{(m)-1} \mathbf{X}_* + \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\vartheta_*}^{-1} \right)^{-1} &= \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\vartheta_*} - \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\vartheta_*} \mathbf{X}'_* \mathbf{F}^{-1} \mathbf{X}_* \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\vartheta_*} \\ &= \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\vartheta_*} - \mathbf{K}_* \mathbf{X}_* \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\vartheta_*} \\ &= (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{K}_* \mathbf{X}_*) \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\vartheta_*} \\ \mathbf{K}_* &= \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\vartheta_*} \mathbf{X}'_* \mathbf{F}^{-1} \\ \mathbf{F} &= \mathbf{H}^{(m)-1} + \mathbf{X}_* \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\vartheta_*} \mathbf{X}'_*,\end{aligned}\tag{72}$$

and the parameters update $\widehat{\boldsymbol{\vartheta}}_\star^{(m+1)}$ becomes

$$\begin{aligned}\widehat{\boldsymbol{\vartheta}}_\star^{(m+1)} &= \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\vartheta_\star} - \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\vartheta_\star} \mathbf{X}'_\star \mathbf{F}^{-1} \mathbf{X}_\star \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\vartheta_\star} + \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\vartheta_\star} \mathbf{X}'_\star \mathbf{H}^{(m)-1} \mathbf{y} - \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\vartheta_\star} \mathbf{X}'_\star \mathbf{F}^{-1} \mathbf{X}_\star \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\vartheta_\star} \mathbf{X}'_\star \mathbf{H}^{(m)-1} \mathbf{y} \\ &= \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\vartheta_\star} - \mathbf{K}_\star \mathbf{X}_\star \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\vartheta_\star} + \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\vartheta_\star} \mathbf{X}'_\star \mathbf{H}^{(m)-1} \mathbf{y} - \mathbf{K}_\star \mathbf{X}_\star \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\vartheta_\star} \mathbf{X}'_\star \mathbf{H}^{(m)-1} \mathbf{y} \end{aligned} \quad (73)$$

$$= \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\vartheta_\star} + \mathbf{K}_\star (\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{X}_\star \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\vartheta_\star}), \quad (74)$$

where the last result follows immediately by observing that, from the definition of the Kalman gain $\mathbf{K}_\star (\mathbf{H}^{(m)-1} + \mathbf{X}_\star \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\vartheta_\star} \mathbf{X}'_\star) = \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\vartheta_\star} \mathbf{X}'_\star$, and

$$\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\vartheta_\star} \mathbf{X}'_\star \mathbf{H}^{(m)-1} \mathbf{y} = \mathbf{K}_\star \mathbf{H}^{(m)} \mathbf{H}^{(m)-1} \mathbf{y} + \mathbf{K}_\star \mathbf{X}_\star \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\vartheta_\star} \mathbf{X}'_\star \mathbf{H}^{(m)-1} \mathbf{y}, \quad (75)$$

which in then substituted into equation (73), yields equation (74).

A.2 Update of ν_1

Concerning the solution for ν_1 observe that the update is the solution of the following equation wrt ν_1 :

$$\widehat{\nu}_1^{(m+1)} = \arg \max_{\nu_1 \in \mathbb{R}^+} \mathcal{Q}_{\nu_1}, \quad (76)$$

where $\mathcal{Q}_{\nu_1} = \mathcal{Q}_{\nu_1,1} + \mathcal{Q}_{\nu_1,2} + \mathcal{Q}_{\nu_1,3}$

$$\mathcal{Q}_{\nu_1,j,1} = -\frac{1}{2} \widehat{\log(b_j)}^{(m+1)} \quad (77)$$

$$\mathcal{Q}_{\nu_1,j,2} = -\frac{1}{2} \widehat{\beta_j}^{(m+1)2} \widehat{b_j^{-1}}^{(m+1)} \quad (78)$$

$$\mathcal{Q}_{\nu_1,j,3} = -(a + b + 2) \log(1 + \nu_{1,j}) + b \log(\nu_{1,j}). \quad (79)$$

Now, substituting for the expressions of $\widehat{\log(b_j)}^{(m+1)}$ and $\widehat{b_j^{-1}}^{(m+1)}$ into previous equations and differentiating with respect to ν_1 , the FOC of the optimisation problem becomes $\frac{\mathcal{Q}_{\nu_1}}{\partial \nu_1} = 0$, where

$$\frac{\mathcal{Q}_{\nu_1,j,1}}{\partial \nu_{1,j}} = -\frac{\widehat{\gamma_j}^{(m+1)}}{2\nu_{1,j}} = 0 \quad (80)$$

$$\frac{\mathcal{Q}_{\nu_1,j,2}}{\partial \nu_{1,j}} = \frac{\widehat{\beta_j}^{(m+1)2} \widehat{\gamma_j}^{(m+1)}}{2\nu_{1,j}^2} = 0 \quad (81)$$

$$\frac{\mathcal{Q}_{\nu_1,j,3}}{\partial \nu_{1,j}} = -\frac{a + b + 2}{1 + \nu_{1,j}} + \frac{b}{\nu_{1,j}} = 0, \quad (82)$$

for $j = 1, 2, \dots, p$, leading to the following set of equations

$$\frac{A_j}{\nu_{1,j}^2} - \frac{a+b+2}{1+\nu_{1,j}} + \frac{B_j+b}{\nu_{1,j}} = 0 \quad (83)$$

$$-(a+b+2)\nu_{1,j}^2 + (B_j+b)\nu_{1,j}(1+\nu_{1,j}) + A_j(1+\nu_{1,j}) = 0 \quad (84)$$

$$(B_j-a-2)\nu_{1,j}^2 + (A_j+B_j+b)\nu_{1,j} + A_j = 0. \quad (85)$$

Therefore we have that

$$\widehat{\nu}_{1,j}^{(m+1)} = \frac{-(A_j+B_j+b) - \Delta_j}{2(B_j-a-2)} \quad (86)$$

$$\Delta_j = \sqrt{(A_j+B_j+b)^2 - 4(B_j-a-2)A_j} \quad (87)$$

where $B_j = -\frac{\widehat{\gamma}_j^{(m)}}{2} < 0$ and $A_j = \frac{1}{2}\widehat{\beta}_j^{(m+1)2}\widehat{\gamma}_j^{(m)} > 0$ for $j = 1, 2, \dots, p$ and $\widehat{\nu}_1^{(m+1)} = \left(\widehat{\nu}_{1,1}^{(m+1)}, \widehat{\nu}_{1,2}^{(m+1)}, \dots, \widehat{\nu}_{1,p}^{(m+1)}\right)'$, $B = (B_1, B_2, \dots, B_p)'$ and $A = (A_1, A_2, \dots, A_p)'$, defined in equations (??)-(55).

B Number of financial firms by country

country	BAN	BRO	INS	OTH	Total	country	BAN	BRO	INS	OTH	Total
ARGENTINA	6	0	0	3	9	LITHUANIA	1	0	0	1	2
AUSTRALIA	4	6	6	15	31	LUXEMBOURG	1	1	0	7	9
AUSTRIA	4	1	2	2	9	MALAYSIA	7	0	2	9	18
BAHRAIN	6	2	1	3	12	MALTA	2	0	1	3	6
BELGIUM	2	1	2	17	22	MEXICO	4	4	0	7	15
BERMUDA	0	2	7	1	10	MONACO	1	0	0	1	2
BRAZIL	4	2	2	5	13	MOROCCO	7	0	4	4	15
BULGARIA	5	0	0	8	13	NETHERLANDS	2	5	3	8	18
CANADA	8	2	7	17	34	NEW ZEALAND	1	0	0	7	8
CHILE	6	2	2	4	14	NIGERIA	11	0	1	2	14
CHINA	2	6	3	3	14	NORWAY	4	1	3	1	9
COLOMBIA	7	3	0	1	11	OMAN	6	0	1	1	8
CROATIA	3	0	2	1	6	PAKISTAN	4	0	1	0	5
CYPRUS	2	2	0	9	13	PERU	5	1	3	2	11
CZECH R.	1	1	0	1	3	PHILIPPINES	7	0	0	6	13
DENMARK	3	0	3	2	8	POLAND	9	0	1	2	12
EGYPT	7	2	0	4	13	PORTUGAL	2	0	0	2	4
ESTONIA	0	0	0	3	3	QATAR	5	1	3	5	14
FINLAND	2	0	1	3	6	ROMANIA	1	1	0	4	6
FRANCE	2	5	5	17	29	RUSSIA	3	1	1	1	6
GERMANY	6	1	3	18	28	SINGAPORE	1	2	1	23	27
GREECE	3	1	2	4	10	SLOVAKIA	2	1	0	1	4
GUERNSEY	0	0	0	9	9	SLOVENIA	0	1	3	3	7
HONG KONG	3	3	2	22	30	SOUTH AFRICA	5	1	5	5	16
HUNGARY	1	3	1	3	8	SPAIN	5	3	2	12	22
INDIA	18	1	1	3	23	SRI LANKA	7	0	0	2	9
INDONESIA	6	0	1	4	11	SWEDEN	2	2	0	9	13
IRELAND	1	1	1	2	5	SWITZERLAND	10	6	7	12	35
ISLE OF MAN	0	0	0	1	1	TAIWAN	5	2	3	1	11
ISRAEL	5	0	3	8	16	THAILAND	6	0	0	3	9
ITALY	16	2	4	6	28	TURKEY	5	1	0	1	7
JAPAN	56	11	6	50	123	U.A.E	15	1	0	6	22
JERSEY	0	1	0	1	2	U.K.	10	13	11	90	124
JORDAN	7	0	0	4	11	U.S.	32	18	29	63	142
KOREA S.	4	3	2	0	9	VENEZUELA	5	1	0	4	10
KUWAIT	2	1	0	4	7						
LIECHT.	1	0	0	0	1	Total	396	132	154	566	1,248

Table 5: List of financial firms considered in the analysis according their type. The period is from the 29th December 2000 to 6th October 2017 at a weekly frequency. The list of the firms is available upon request.

C Analysis on market returns with additional set of variables

We provide an additional analysis to check if the hubs-indicator maintain its explanatory power on the market returns, we perform a further regression by including other three set of predictors lagged at one and four periods,

- Changes in volatility indices: VIX (U.S.), VSTOXX (EURO STOXX 50), VHSI (Hong Kong) and VNKY (Nikkei). Results are included in Table 6;
- Changes in financial stress indicators such as the CISS and the STLFSI (Table 7);
- The Fama and French 5 global factors (Fama and French, 2015): i) Mkt-Rf (the market's excess return); ii) SMB (Small Minus Big); iii) HML (High Minus Low); iv) RMW (Robust Minus Weak) and v) CMA (Conservative Minus Aggressive).⁶ Results are reported in Table 8.

As a further test, we performed the regressions by including also the contemporaneous variables. For all the cases, the hubs indicator results not statistically significant at t .⁷

⁶The Fama and French 5 factors makes use of 6 value-weight portfolios formed on size and book-to-market, the 6 value-weight portfolios formed on size and operating profitability, and the 6 value-weight portfolios formed on size and investment. For further information, see http://mba.tuck.dartmouth.edu/pages/faculty/ken.french/Data_Library/f-f_5_factors_2x3.html.

⁷Result are available upon request to the authors.

	estimate	s.e.	t-stat	p-value
<i>mean equation</i>				
(constant)	0.0008	0.0011	0.7200	0.4700
r_{t-1}	0.0282	0.0537	0.5300	0.5990
$\log(h_{t-1})$	0.5459	1.6743	0.3300	0.7440
$\Delta\xi_{t-1}$	-0.1277	0.0346	-3.6900	0.0000
$\Delta\xi_{t-4}$	0.1042	0.0489	2.1300	0.0330
ΔVIX_{t-1}	-0.0006	0.0006	-1.0000	0.3150
ΔVIX_{t-4}	-0.0011	0.0005	-2.0500	0.0400
$\Delta\text{VSTOXX}_{t-1}$	0.0009	0.0005	1.8100	0.0710
$\Delta\text{VSTOXX}_{t-4}$	0.0003	0.0005	0.6400	0.5210
ΔVHSI_{t-1}	0.0005	0.0004	1.0800	0.2800
ΔVHSI_{t-4}	-0.0001	0.0005	-0.2200	0.8290
ΔVNKY_{t-1}	0.0000	0.0004	0.1000	0.9170
ΔVNKY_{t-4}	0.0003	0.0003	1.0100	0.3120
<i>volatility equation</i>				
(constant)	-0.1645	0.0510	-3.2200	0.0010
z_{t-1}	-0.1418	0.0141	-10.0500	0.0000
$ z_{t-1} - E z_{t-1} $	0.0622	0.0236	2.6300	0.0080
$\log(h_{t-1})$	0.9784	0.0068	143.5200	0.0000
obs	767		Wald $\chi^2(12)$	31.33
Log-likelihood	1786.77		Prob > χ^2	0.0018

Table 6: Estimates for the AR(1)-EGARCH-m(1,1) model by including the (lagged) changes in the hubs indicator $\Delta\xi_t$ and the changes in volatility indices: VIX CBOE (S&P 500), VSTOXX (EURO STOXX 50), VHSI (Hong Kong) and VNKY (Nikkei).

	estimate	s.e.	t-stat	p-value
<i>mean equation</i>				
(constant)	0.0010	0.0010	1.0200	0.3090
r_{t-1}	-0.0277	0.0406	-0.6800	0.4950
$\log(h_{t-1})$	0.2719	1.5517	0.1800	0.8610
$\Delta\xi_{t-1}$	-0.1329	0.0339	-3.9200	0.0000
$\Delta\xi_{t-4}$	0.0965	0.0484	1.9900	0.0460
ΔCISS_{t-1}	0.0002	0.0227	0.0100	0.9940
ΔCISS_{t-4}	-0.0005	0.0228	-0.0200	0.9840
$\Delta\text{STLFSI}_{t-1}$	0.0024	0.0094	0.2600	0.7950
$\Delta\text{STLFSI}_{t-4}$	-0.0083	0.0112	-0.7400	0.4590
<i>volatility equation</i>				
(constant)	-0.1560	0.0490	-3.1900	0.0010
z_{t-1}	-0.1395	0.0152	-9.1700	0.0000
$ z_{t-1} - E z_{t-1} $	0.0582	0.0221	2.6300	0.0090
$\log(h_{t-1})$	0.9796	0.0065	149.6100	0.0000
obs	767		Wald $\chi^2(8)$	18.57
Log-likelihood	1781.07		Prob> χ^2	0.0173

Table 7: Estimates for the AR(1)-EGARCH-m(1,1) model by including the (lagged) changes in the hubs indicator $\Delta\xi_t$ and the changes in financial stress indicators such as the CISS and the STLFSI.

	estimate	s.e.	t-stat	p-value
<i>mean equation</i>				
(constant)	0.0008	0.0010	0.8200	0.4130
r_{t-1}	-0.1105	0.0931	-1.1900	0.2350
$\log(h_{t-1})$	0.4977	1.4337	0.3500	0.7280
$\Delta\xi_{t-1}$	-0.1432	0.0339	-4.2300	0.0000
$\Delta\xi_{t-4}$	0.1077	0.0487	2.2100	0.0270
Mkt-Rf $_{t-1}$	0.0672	0.1052	0.6400	0.5230
SMB $_{t-1}$	0.0216	0.1094	0.2000	0.8440
MHL $_{t-1}$	0.1028	0.1354	0.7600	0.4480
RMW $_{t-1}$	-0.2065	0.1883	-1.1000	0.2730
CMA $_{t-1}$	-0.0113	0.1911	-0.0600	0.9530
<i>volatility equation</i>				
(constant)	-0.1603	0.0528	-3.0300	0.0020
z_{t-1}	-0.1452	0.0153	-9.5000	0.0000
$ z_{t-1} - E z_{t-1} $	0.0507	0.0234	2.1700	0.0300
$\log(h_{t-1})$	0.9791	0.0071	138.6100	0.0000
obs	767		Wald $\chi^2(9)$	24.00
Log-likelihood	1782.43		Prob> χ^2	0.0043

Table 8: Estimates for the AR(1)-EGARCH-m(1,1) model by including the (lagged) changes in the hubs indicator $\Delta\xi_t$ and the Fama and French 5 factors (Fama and French, 2015).

References

- Acemoglu, D., Ozdaglar, A., and Tahbaz-Salehi, A. (2015). Systemic risk and stability in financial networks. *American Economic Review*, 105(2):564–608.
- Acharya, V., Engle, R., and Richardson, M. (2012). Capital shortfall: A new approach to ranking and regulating systemic risks. *American Economic Review*, 102(3):59–64.
- Adrian, T. and Brunnermeier, M. K. (2016). Covar. *American Economic Review*, 106(7):1705–41.
- Ahelegbey, D. F., Billio, M., and Casarin, R. (2016). Bayesian graphical models for structural vector autoregressive processes. *Journal of Applied Econometrics*, 31(2):357–386.
- Allen, F. and Babus, A. (2009). Networks in finance. *The network challenge*, pages 367–382.
- Ardia, D. (2008). *Financial risk management with Bayesian estimation of GARCH models*, volume 612 of *Lecture Notes in Economics and Mathematical Systems*. Springer-Verlag, Berlin. Theory and applications.
- Barabási, A.-L. and Albert, R. (1999). Emergence of scaling in random networks. *science*, 286(5439):509–512.
- Barabási, A.-L. and Bonabeau, E. (2003). Scale-free networks. *Scientific american*, 288(5):60–69.
- Barigozzi, M. and Brownlees, C. T. (2016). Nets: Network estimation for time series.
- Bianchi, D., Billio, M., Casarin, R., and Guidolin, M. (2015). Modeling contagion and systemic risk. *Journal of Econometrics*, forthcoming.
- Billio, M., Caporin, M., Frattarolo, L., and Pelizzon, L. (2018). Networks in risk spillovers: a multivariate garch perspective.
- Billio, M., Caporin, M., Panzica, R. C., and Pelizzon, L. (2016). The impact of network connectivity on factor exposures, asset pricing and portfolio diversification.
- Billio, M., Getmansky, M., Lo, A., and Pellizon, L. (2012). Econometric measures of connectedness and systemic risk in the finance and insurance sectors. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 101:535–559.
- Boss, M., Elsinger, H., Summer, M., and Thurner 4, S. (2004). Network topology of the interbank market. *Quantitative finance*, 4(6):677–684.

- Castillo, E. and Hadi, A. S. (1997). Fitting the generalized pareto distribution to data. *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, 92(440):1609–1620.
- Corsi, F. (2009). A simple approximate long-memory model of realized volatility. *Journal of Financial Econometrics*, 7(2):174–196.
- Demirer, M., Diebold, F. X., Liu, L., and Yilmaz, K. (2017). Estimating global bank network connectedness. *Journal of Applied Econometrics*.
- Demos, A. and Sentana, E. (1998). An em algorithm for conditionally heteroscedastic factor models. *Journal of Business & Economic Statistics*, 16(3):357–361.
- Diebold, F. X. and Yilmaz, K. (2014). On the network topology of variance decompositions: Measuring the connectedness of financial firms. *Journal of Econometrics*, 182(1):119–134.
- Efron, B., Hastie, T., Johnstone, I., and Tibshirani, R. (2004). Least angle regression. *Ann. Statist.*, 32(2):407–499.
- Elliott, M., Golub, B., and Jackson, M. O. (2014). Financial networks and contagion. *American Economic Review*, 104(10):3115–53.
- Embrechts, P., Klüppelberg, C., and Mikosch, T. (2013). *Modelling extremal events: for insurance and finance*, volume 33. Springer Science & Business Media.
- Engle, R. F. and Bollerslev, T. (1986). Modelling the persistence of conditional variances. *Econometric Rev.*, 5(1):1–87. With comments and a reply by the authors.
- Fama, E. F. and French, K. R. (2015). A five-factor asset pricing model. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 116(1):1 – 22.
- Hollo, D., Kremer, M., and Lo Duca, M. (2012). CISS - a composite indicator of systemic stress in the financial system. *ECB Working Paper Series*, 1426.
- Iori, G., De Masi, G., Precup, O. V., Gabbi, G., and Caldarelli, G. (2008). A network analysis of the italian overnight money market. *Journal of Economic Dynamics and Control*, 32(1):259–278.
- Kliesen, K. L., Smith, D. C., et al. (2010). Measuring financial market stress. *economic synopses*.
- Korobilis, D. and Yilmaz, K. (2018). Measuring dynamic connectedness with large bayesian var models.

- McLachlan, G. and Krishnan, T. (2007). *The EM algorithm and extensions*, volume 382. John Wiley & Sons.
- Müller, U. A., Dacorogna, M. M., Davé, R. D., Olsen, R. B., Pictet, O. V., and von Weizsäcker, J. E. (1997). Volatilities of different time resolutions analyzing the dynamics of market components. *Journal of Empirical Finance*, 4(2-3):213–239.
- Peel, D. and McLachlan, G. J. (2000). Robust mixture modelling using the t distribution. *Statistics and Computing*, 10(4):339–348.
- Pickands III, J. (1975). Statistical inference using extreme order statistics. *The Annals of Statistics*, pages 119–131.
- Schweitzer, F., Fagiolo, G., Sornette, D., Vega-Redondo, F., Vespignani, A., and White, D. R. (2009). Economic networks: The new challenges. *science*, 325(5939):422–425.
- Shumway, T. (1997). The delisting bias in crsp data. *The Journal of Finance*, 52(1):327–340.
- Tibshirani, R. (1996). Regression shrinkage and selection via the lasso. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society, Series B*, 58:267–288.
- Yuan, M. and Lin, Y. (2006). Model selection and estimation in regression with grouped variables. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society: Series B (Statistical Methodology)*, 68(1):49–67.
- Zou, H. (2006). The adaptive lasso and its oracle properties. *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, 101(476):1418–1429.